

Welcome to the June newsletter where you can find out all about the LNL retreat in Newcastle and discover lots of events and resources to share with your local network. Enjoy!

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Group photo of LNLs and some of the UKRN team at our Newcastle Retreat last week.

2024 LNL retreat in Newcastle

We're delighted to say that LNL Sam Westwood used his train journey home from this year's LNL retreat to write a blog on his retreat reflections. You can read his blog [here](#).

Below are some edited highlights from both Sam Westwood and Dolly Coates, the UKRN Project Coordinator:

A central feature of the UKRN is supporting its grassroots community of over 90 local network leads (LNLs) from 80 UK universities. One way we do this is by hosting an annual retreat, and this year's was hosted by Newcastle University. The retreat aims to strengthen links between LNLs, open conversations on key topics, and identify practical ways to overcome challenges.

On the first day, discussions opened around what the role of an LNL is, and the need for both activist and advocacy work. Related discussions circled around the many advantages of being an LNL, including increased credibility with institutions, leadership opportunities, sharing learning with colleagues, and in some cases successfully arguing for workloaded time to pursue LNL activities.

The second day of the retreat saw the introduction of the new LNL guidebook, a comprehensive guide for current and future LNLs. The guidebook defines what an LNL is and where they sit in the UKRN infrastructure, three broad aims LNLs ought to pursue, and the advantages of being an LNL.

Broader discussion opened out on the future direction of the UKRN, potential collaborations with the growing number of 20 or so national Reproducibility Networks, funding opportunities, and the development of resources to support our growing community.

Upcoming LNL workshops

Workshop 6: Writing Retreat

We are running another all day writing retreat - it's an opportunity for some light social activity, as well as carving out a solid block of time to dedicate to writing/coding/analysis. Set your out-of-office and devote maximum headspace to your task. The day will be led by Sarah Gunn, LNL University of Leicester. 10 July 9:30 – 16:00 (optional later finish at 17:30) Register [here](#)

December workshop: Replication games – all day event

It's a long way off but we're so excited we wanted to share the details with you. This will be an all-day event run by Abel Brodeur from the [Institute for Replication](#). Consider it an early Christmas present from us to you. More details to follow. 5 December 9:30 – 17:30 Register [here](#)

Other UKRN resources

LNL Guidebook and UKRN stickers

The newly created LNL Guidebook was launched at the LNL Retreat. Copies will be posted to LNLs who were unable to attend.

We have also just ordered some of the ever-popular UKRN stickers and we will post these out alongside the guidebooks. Feel free to plaster your laptop, phone, office door, fridge, children and guinea pigs with these lovely little items.

Upcoming UKRN webinars

[UKRN: A Space Odyssey \(a journey through the STAR and METEOR projects\)](#)

June 20, 2024 13:00 - 15:00

Learn more about these two UKRN projects, co-funded by UKRN's members. STAR (Sustainable and TrAnsparent Research data) reviews the arrangements institutions have in place to support open data. METEOR (METa-research for the Enhancement of Research culture) explores how institutions use research evidence to inform their research culture. This webinar will present preliminary findings and emerging themes from both projects. Q&A session. Register [here](#)

Speakers:

Jess Wheeler: Senior Research Associate in Qualitative Research, Project Lead for STAR

Pen-Yuan Hsing: Senior Research Associate, STAR project

Robbie Clark: Research Associate, METEOR project

Ros Strang: Project Coordinator, STAR and METEOR projects

[UKRN: An update on the Community Project](#)

July 18, 2024 13:00 - 15:00

Will Gawned and colleagues will present an update on the various Community Project activities and initiatives, and discuss our next steps. Register [here](#)

Other events

[Science communication and research integrity](#)

Wed, 26 Jun 2024 10:00 - 11:00 BST

This is the latest in the series of regular free webinars from the [UK Research Integrity Office](#) on research integrity and related issues. Is research integrity relevant to science communication, also known as 'scicomm': the communication of science beyond researchers? Our speaker will discuss how scicomm should consider the rigour of the original research and its publication process, including any peer review, and principles relevant for scicomm, such as accuracy, transparency, and declaration of interests.

Speaker:

Dr Stephen Webster, Senior Lecturer in Science Communication, Imperial College London and Director of The Good Science Project

[The LMU & MPG Open Science Summer School 2024](#)

This intensive 5-day Open Science Summer School provides early career researchers with the knowledge and skills to make their research

more **transparent**, **reproducible** and **credible** in the eyes of their peers, the public and funding agencies.

By joining (or accessing the material after the school), you will learn how to:

- clarify your research design and set up your statistical plans in advance of collecting data to prevent biases in analyses, with the help of **preregistration** and **data simulation**;
- create computationally reproducible workflows so you can be more efficient and spot mistakes in data wrangling or analyses, through **programming** with **version controlled** scripts;
- prepare, manage and share **data** and **code** in connection with your **articles** by applying the **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principles**, and using adequate **repositories** and **licenses**.

Increase the **impact** of your research and secure the **acknowledgement** of your and others contributions by opening your research practices!

[Programme details](#)

To attend the whole Summer School, i.e. both public lectures and workshops for selected applicants, in person or online, you must **apply before 15 July 2024**.

KING'S
College
LONDON

Open Research Summer School

22-26 July 2024

Learn more about Reproducibility, Transparency,
Error Detection & Academic Fraud

All welcome

Institute of Psychiatry, Psychology & Neuroscience
16 De Crespigny Park, London SE5 8AF

REGISTER HERE

[Open Research Summer School](#)

22 - 26 July 2024

This event is co-organised by the RIOT Science Club and the Research Innovation Committee, and funded by the Health Science Doctoral Training Centre at King's College London. An exciting week of talks and roundtable discussions, hands-on workshops and networking opportunities.

Speakers include: Dr Emma Henderson, Professor Dorothy Bishop, Professor Daniel Lakens, Dr Nick Brown, Professor Federico Turkheimer, Professor Sarah Byford, Dr Anthony Pelosi, Dr Dale Barr, Dr Ian Hussey, Professor Mitul Mehta, and many more.

Register [here](#).

Reading recommendations

[Research culture in biomedicine: what we learned, and what we would like to do about it](#)

A report by Alexa McCray and colleagues on work done at Harvard Medical School to identify areas for improvement in research rigour, reproducibility, and responsibility in pursuit of continued research excellence.

Survey on evaluating research

Springer Nature is carrying out an anonymous global study to gather researchers' views about the way their work is evaluated, and how they would like to see this develop in the future.

- How appropriate is the current way in which your work is evaluated?
- What aspects of your work should be measured to indicate success?
- How can the administrative load of this evaluation be improved?

This work will lead to a variety of outcomes, including published reports and discussions with funders and institutions on initiatives to address how research is evaluated.

The survey link is [here](#). Closing date: 26 July 2024

Do you have events to share?

Are you planning an event that you would like us to promote? Get in touch contact@ukrn.org and we'll do just that.
